

Effects Of the Inhibitory Mechanism and Language Script on Bilingual Language Control

Mevla Yahya¹, Aslı Yörük Sevinçli², Zebide Ibraimi¹, Agron Rustemi¹, and Merita Zulfiu-Alili¹,

¹Department of Psychology, South East European University, Tetovo & Skopje, North
Macedonia

²Department of Psychology, Hacettepe University, Ankara, Türkiye

Author Note

Mevla Yahya <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5050-6665>

Aslı Yörük Sevinçli <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9975-6689>

Zebide Ibraimi

Agron Rustemi

Merita Zulfiu Alili

We have no conflicts of interests to disclosure.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Mevla Yahya, South East

European University, Ilindenska 335, 1200, Tetovo, North Macedonia. E-mail:

mevlayahya@gmail.com

Acknowledgements: Special thanks to bachelor's students of the Department of Psychology at South East European University, for their assistance with the data collection procedures.

Effects Of the Inhibitory Mechanism and Language Script on Bilingual Language Control

A key difference between monolingual and bilingual language processing is that bilinguals activate words from both of their languages at the same time (e.g., Costa et al., 1999; Kroll et al., 2012; Thierry & Wu, 2007). This parallel activation can lead to interference between languages, which must be resolved for successful communication. The process that manages this interference is known as *language control* (Declerck & Koch, 2023; Runnqvist et al., 2011).

One influential view is that language control relies on inhibitory mechanisms that suppress the non-target language, allowing the correct language to be selected (Green, 1998; see Declerck & Koch, 2023). According to this account, stronger languages (typically the native language, L1) require stronger inhibition when the weaker language (L2) is used.

Much of the evidence for this comes from the language-switching paradigm, where bilinguals switch between languages while naming stimuli. A consistent finding is that responses are slower and more error-prone on switch trials than on repetition trials. This difference is called the *switch cost* (Bobb & Wodniecka, 2013; Declerck & Philipp, 2015) and reflects the effort needed to select the target language and overcome interference from the previous one.

Importantly, switch costs are often *asymmetrical*: switching into L1 is typically more costly than switching into L2 (Bobb & Wodniecka, 2013; Declerck & Koch, 2023). This has been interpreted as evidence for inhibition, because L1 (the dominant language) is assumed to be more strongly suppressed when L2 is used, and therefore harder to reactivate (Green, 1998; Meuter & Allport, 1999).

To test the role of inhibition, researchers have combined the language-switching paradigm with the Stroop task (Stroop, 1935), which measures cognitive control. In the Stroop task, participants name the ink color of words that can be congruent (e.g., red printed in red ink)

or incongruent (e.g., red printed in green ink) with the word meaning. Incongruent trials create conflict because the tendency to read the word interferes with color identification. Therefore correct naming in incongruent trials and require inhibition to resolve that conflict (MacLeod, 1991).

The language-switching paradigm can be integrated into the Stroop task by presenting congruent and incongruent color words in both the L1 and L2 and manipulating whether the stimulus language is the same as on the previous trial (language repetition) or different (language switch) (e.g., Liu et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2020; Williams et al., 2025; Yahya & Ozkan Ceylan, 2022; Yahya et al., 2025). This allows researchers to test whether language control and general inhibitory control rely on shared mechanisms. If they do, switch costs should increase under Stroop conflict.

However, findings have been mixed. Some studies (e.g., Liu et al., 2019) report larger switch costs under conflict, especially for L1, supporting shared inhibition. Others (e.g., Williams et al., 2025) find no such interaction. Additionally, some studies report interactions without asymmetrical switch costs (Yahya & Ozkan Ceylan, 2022), which challenges the idea that inhibition is proportional to language dominance.

Another factor that may influence results is script similarity. Some studies suggest that using different writing systems affects switching performance (Slevc et al., 2016), but recent findings are inconsistent (Williams et al., 2025; Yahya et al., 2025).

Further evidence comes from *sequential congruency effects* (SCE), where Stroop interference is reduced after an incongruent trial. SCEs are often seen as reflecting reactive control processes (Gratton et al., 1992; Egner, 2014). Yahya and Ozkan Ceylan (2022), reported

reduced SCEs during language switching, which may suggest that switching relies less on trial-by-trial reactive control and more on sustained control processes.

In general, cognitive control can be divided into two modes: *reactive* and *proactive* (Braver, 2012). Reactive control is triggered after conflict is detected, whereas proactive control involves maintaining task goals in advance to prevent conflict. These modes differ in timing and efficiency, with proactive control typically leading to faster and more stable performance (Braver et al., 2009, 2021).

Bilingual language control is thought to involve both modes. Reactive control is reflected in measures such as asymmetrical switch costs and N-2 repetition costs, which indicate temporary inhibition. Proactive control is reflected in patterns such as reversed language dominance and blocked language order effects, which suggest sustained adjustments to language activation (Declerck, 2020; Declerck & Koch, 2023).

Overall, existing research suggests that inhibition plays a role in bilingual language control. However, inconsistent findings, such as variable switch costs, lack of asymmetries, and mixed Stroop effects, indicate that a purely reactive inhibition account is insufficient. Instead, language control appears to be flexible and shaped by both proactive and reactive processes.

Despite this, previous studies using combined Stroop and language-switching tasks have not directly manipulated control mode. Instead, they have treated Stroop interference as a single process.

One established way to manipulate control mode is by varying the proportion of incongruent trials in the Stroop task. A high proportion of incongruent trials encourages proactive control, as participants expect conflict. In contrast, a low proportion encourages reactive control, as conflict is less predictable (Gonthier et al., 2016; Grandjean et al., 2012).

Study Questions

The present study examines how bilingual language control interacts with proactive and reactive control demands. Participants will name the ink color of incongruent color words and neutral (non-color) words. Neutral trials are used to isolate interference effects without facilitation from congruent trials (as congruent trials primarily reflect facilitation rather than a control condition).

Stimuli will appear in either L1 or L2, and trials will either repeat or switch language. Participants will complete two task versions: one with mostly incongruent trials (proactive condition) and one with mostly neutral trials (reactive condition).

To examine the role of script, two studies will be conducted. Study 1 will test Macedonian–English bilinguals (different scripts: Cyrillic vs. Latin), while Study 2 will test Albanian–English bilinguals (same script: Latin).

Hypotheses

We predict a Control Type \times Language interaction, such that reversed language dominance (worse performance in L1) will be stronger in the proactive condition. This would indicate sustained proactive control.

We also predict a Control Type \times Language \times Switch Type interaction, with larger asymmetrical switch costs in the reactive condition. This would reflect transient, reactive inhibition. This effect is expected to be stronger in Study 1 (Macedonian-English bilinguals using different scripts).

Method

This study was approved by the Hacettepe University Social Sciences and Humanities Research Ethics Committee. Each participant will provide written informed consent before participation.

Study Design

This project consists of two independent but closely related studies. In both studies, bilingual participants will complete a combined language-switching and Stroop task adapted to their language pair. Study 1 includes Macedonian–English bilinguals, while Study 2 includes Albanian–English bilinguals.

Both studies use a 2 (Control Type: Proactive vs. Reactive) \times 2 (Trial Type: Incongruent vs. Neutral) \times 2 (Language: L1 vs. L2) \times 2 (Switch Type: Switch vs. Repetition) within-subjects design. The main dependent variables are reaction times and accuracy.

Participants

Two groups of bilingual participants will be recruited. Study 1 will include Macedonian–English bilinguals, and Study 2 will include Albanian–English bilinguals. The target sample size is at least 20 participants per study. Participant classification as bilingual will be determined using the Language and Social Background Questionnaire (Anderson et al., 2018).

Participants must meet the following inclusion criteria: (1) aged 18–30 years, (2) currently enrolled in or having completed higher education, (3) no history of neurological or psychiatric disorders, and (4) no regular use of psychiatric medication or psychoactive substances in the past few months.

Data Collection Instruments

Language and Social Background Questionnaire (LSBQ)

The Language and Social Background Questionnaire (LSBQ) will be used to identify bilingual participants. The original questionnaire was developed by Anderson et al. (2018).

The LSBQ consists of three sections: Demographic Information, Language Background, and Community Language Use Behavior. The first section does not contribute directly to bilingualism scoring; it only collects demographic data. The second section assesses known languages, age and context of acquisition, proficiency across four language skills, and degree of language exposure. The third section examines language use across life periods, interlocutors, and frequency of language switching.

Responses from the second and third sections yield three factor scores (L2 home use and proficiency, L2 social use, and L1 proficiency) and one *composite score*. According to Anderson et al. (2018), individuals with a *composite factor score* of ≥ 1.2 are classified as bilingual, and those scoring ≤ -3.1 as monolingual. In our study, participants who score > 1.2 will be invited to complete the experimental task.

Combined Language Switching and Stroop Task

The Stroop Task is a well-established paradigm used to examine inhibitory control and attentional processes (Stroop, 1935). Participants are presented with color words printed in various ink colors. In incongruent trials, the semantic meaning of the word and ink color mismatch (e.g., “blue” printed in red), whereas in congruent trials, the word and ink color match (e.g., “blue” in blue). Participants are instructed to identify the ink color as quickly and accurately as possible while ignoring the word meaning. The Stroop effect i.e., slower responses and higher errors on incongruent trials, reflects the cognitive cost of resolving conflict.

The present study will employ Proactive and Reactive versions of the Stroop Task, adapted from Grandjean et al. (2012) using PsychoPy 3. In both versions, participants will see color words (red, blue, green, yellow) and neutral words (door, ship, number or apple, and cup respectively) displayed in colored ink. Importantly, the task will integrate language-switching by presenting stimuli in participants' L1 and L2. On each trial, the stimulus language will either repeat from the previous trial or switch to the other language. Participants will be instructed to name the ink color as quickly and accurately as possible, using the language in which the stimulus is presented (see Figure 1).

Importantly, the task will integrate language-switching by presenting stimuli in participants' L1 and L2. On each trial, the stimulus language will either repeat from the previous trial or switch to the other language. Participants will be instructed to name the ink color as quickly and accurately as possible, using the language in which the stimulus is presented (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Trial Types in the Stroop Task

Each trial will begin with the fixation cross presented for 500ms. Then the stimulus will be presented for 2000 ms or until response, followed by a 500 ms blank screen (intertrial interval).

According to the DMC framework, proactive control is encouraged in task contexts with a high proportion of incongruent trials (Etzel et al., 2022; Gonthier et al., 2016a; Grandjean et al., 2012). Accordingly, the Proactive version will contain a high proportion of incongruent trials, whereas the Reactive version contained a high proportion of neutral trials to discourage anticipatory strategies.

Both versions will consist of eight blocks of 33 trials each. The first trial of each block will serve as a filler (always incongruent in the Proactive condition and neutral in the Reactive condition). The distribution of trials across Language (L1 vs. L2), Switch Type (switch vs. repetition), and Trial Type conditions is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Distribution of Trial Counts Across Conditions in the Combined Language Switching and Stroop Tasks.

Proactive Version		
	Neutral	Incongruent
L1 switch	24	40
L1 repeat	24	40
L2 switch	24	40
L2 repeat	24	40
Total	96	160
Trial count in each block	12	20
Reactive Version		
	Neutral	Incongruent
L1 switch	40	24
L1 repeat	40	24
L2 switch	40	24
L2 repeat	40	24
Total	160	96
Trial count in each block	20	12

Note. L1: first language; L2: second language.

Trial sequences were fully counterbalanced with respect to language, switch type, and congruency to ensure balanced presentation across conditions (see Appendix A). Word–ink color pairings were randomized on a trial-by-trial basis, subject to two constraints: successive trials did not share the same ink color, and each word–color pairing occurred equally often across blocks to control for stimulus–response contingency effects (Atalay et al., 2013; Braver et al., 2021; İnan et al., 2018).

Each task version lasted approximately 12 minutes (approximately 25 minutes in total). Prior to the experimental blocks, participants completed a 16-trial practice block with feedback

Procedure

Both Study 1 and Study 2 will be conducted at the Faculty of Contemporary Social Sciences, South East European University (Tetova campus). Participants will be recruited through university notice boards, student groups, and in-class announcements.

Both studies will follow a two-stage procedure. In the first stage, eligibility will be assessed using the Language and Social Background Scale, administered online via Google Forms. Participants who meet the inclusion criteria will be invited to the second stage.

In the second stage, eligible participants will complete the combined language-switching and Stroop task in a laboratory setting. The proactive and reactive versions of the task will be counterbalanced across participants. The task will be programmed in PsychoPy3, and all participants will use the same laptop to ensure consistency in testing conditions. The full session will last approximately 30 minutes.

Data analysis

Data Preprocessing

Reaction time (RT) data will be cleaned by removing filler, error trials, and trials followed by an error. Outliers will be identified and removed separately for each task, participant, and condition using a ± 2.5 standard deviation criterion. These procedures will be implemented to minimize the influence of early trials, errors, and attentional lapses, thereby enhancing internal validity.

Accuracy of the responses will be evaluated post-experiment. Accuracy rates (AR) will be computed as the proportion of correct responses.

Statistical Analyses

RT and AR performance will be analyzed using linear mixed-effects (LME) models (Bates et al., 2015b; Pinheiro et al., 2024). Fixed effects will include *control type* (proactive vs. reactive), *trial type* (incongruent vs. neutral), *language* (L1 vs. L2), *switch type* (switch vs. repeat), and *trial type* (AY, BX and BY). RT models will include random intercepts for *participant* and *trial*, while AR models included random intercepts for *participant* only. Random slopes will not be included in any analysis to maintain model parsimony (Bates et al., 2015a).

All LME analyses will be conducted in RStudio (version 2023.12.1) using the `lme` function from `nlme` (v3.1-164) (Pinheiro et al., 2024). Statistical significance will be assessed with the `anova` function from `lmerTest` (v3.1-3) (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). Effect sizes will be estimated using `sjstats` (v0.19.0) (Lüdtke, 2018), and Bonferroni-corrected post hoc comparisons will be conducted with `emmeans` (v1.10.6) (Lenth, 2023).

References

- Anderson, J. A. E., Mak, L., Keyvani Chahi, A., & Bialystok, E. (2018). The Language and Social Background Questionnaire: Assessing degree of bilingualism in a diverse population. *Behavioral Research Methods*, *50*, 250–263. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-017-0867-9>
- Bates, D., Kliegl, R., Vasishth, S., & Baayen, H. (2015a). Parsimonious mixed models. *arXiv*, 1506.04967v1 382
- Bates, D., Mächler, M., Bolker, B., & Walker, S. (2015b). Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *67*, 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>
- Bobb, S. C., & Wodniecka, Z. (2013). Language switching in picture naming: What asymmetric switch costs (do not) tell us about inhibition in bilingual speech planning. *Journal of Cognitive Psychology*, *25*(5), 568–585. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20445911.2013.792822>
- Braver, T. S. (2012). The variable nature of cognitive control: A dual mechanisms framework. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *16*(2), 106–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2011.12.010>
- Braver, T. S., Kizhner, A., Tang, R., Freund, M. C., & Etzel, J. A. (2021). The Dual Mechanisms of Cognitive Control Project. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 1–26. https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn_a_01768
- Braver, T. S., Paxton, J. L., Locke, H. S., & Barch, D. M. (2009). Flexible neural mechanisms of cognitive control within human prefrontal cortex. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *106*(18), 7351–7356. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0808187106>

- Costa, A., Miozzo, M., & Caramazza, A. (1999). Lexical selection in bilinguals: Do words in the bilingual's two lexicons compete for selection? *Journal of Memory and Language*, *41*(3), 365–397. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmla.1999.2651>
- Declerck M., & Philipp A. M. (2017). Is there lemma-based language control? The influence of language practice and language-specific item practice on asymmetrical switch costs. *Language, Cognition and Neuroscience*, *32*, 488–493.
- Declerck, M. (2020). What about proactive language control? *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, *27*(1), 24–35. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-019-01654-1>
- Declerck, M., & Koch, I. (2023). The concept of inhibition in bilingual control. *Psychological Review*, *130*(4), 953–976. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000367>
- Declerck, M., & Philipp, A. M. (2015). A review of control processes and their locus in language switching. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, *22*(6), 1630–1645. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-015-0836-1>
- Egner, T. (2014). Creatures of habit (and control): A multi-level learning perspective on the modulation of congruency effects. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *5*, Article 1247. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01247>
- Etzel, J. A., Brough, R. E., Freund, M. C., Kizhner, A., Lin, Y., Singh, M. F., ... & Braver, T. S. (2022). The Dual Mechanisms of Cognitive Control dataset, a theoretically-guided within-subject task fMRI battery. *Scientific Data*, *9*(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01226-4>
- Gonthier, C., Braver, T. S., & Bugg, J. M. (2016). Dissociating proactive and reactive control in the Stroop task. *Memory & Cognition*, *44*(5), 778–788. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13421-016-0591-1>

Grandjean, J., D'Ostilio, K., Phillips, C., Balteau, E., Degueldre, C., Luxen, A., ... & Collette, F. (2012). Modulation of brain activity during a Stroop inhibitory task by the kind of cognitive control required. *PLOS ONE*, 7(7), e41513.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0041513>

Gratton, G., Coles, M. G. H., & Donchin, E. (1992). Optimizing the use of information: Strategic control of activation of responses. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 121, 480–506. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.121.4.480>

Green, D. W. (1998). Mental control of the bilingual lexicosemantic system. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 1(2), 67–81. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728998000133>

The jamovi project (2023). *jamovi*. (Version 2.4) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>.

Kroll, J. F., Dussias, P. E., Bogulski, C. A., & Kroff, J. R. V. (2012). Juggling two languages in one mind: What bilinguals tell us about language processing and its consequences for cognition. In B. H. Ross (Ed.), *The psychology of learning and motivation* (pp. 229–262). Elsevier Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-394393-4.00007-8>

Kuznetsova, A., Brockhoff, P. B., & Christensen, R. H. B. (2017). lmerTest package: Tests in linear mixed effects models. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 82(13), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v082.i13>

Lüdecke, D. (2018). Sjstats: Statistical functions for regression models. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.1284472>

- Ma, F., Li, S., & Guo, T. (2016). Reactive and proactive control in bilingual word production: An investigation of influential factors. *Journal of Memory and Language*, *86*, 35–59.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2015.08.004>
- Meuter R. F., & Allport A. (1999). Bilingual language switching in naming: Asymmetrical costs of language selection. *Journal of Memory and Language*, *40*, 25–40.
- Peirce, J. W. (2007). PsychoPy - Psychophysics software in Python. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, *162*(1–2), 8–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2006.11.017>
- Philipp A. M., Gade M., & Koch I. (2007). Inhibitory processes in language switching: Evidence from switching language-defined response sets. *European Journal of Cognitive Psychology*, *19*, 395–416.
- Pinheiro, J., & Bates, D. R. Core Team?? (2024). *nlme: Linear and nonlinear mixed effects models* (R Package® version 3.1-165). <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=nlme>
- Runnqvist, E., Strijkers, K., Sadat, J., & Costa, A. (2011). On the temporal and functional origin of L2 disadvantages in speech production: A critical review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *2*, 379. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2011.00379>
- Thierry, G., & Wu, Y. J. (2007). Brain potentials reveal unconscious translation during foreign-language comprehension. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *104*(30), 12530–12535. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0609927104>